

Critical Judgment whether Palestine is a state under international law? The reason for conflicts and efforts of the International Community for mitigation of skirmish between Israel-Palestine.

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Abstract— Balfour Declaration, November 2, 1917. significantly favors the Jewish colonization in Palestine where natives had ninety and Jewish nine percent of the total population which rose to twenty-seven percent from 1922 to 1935. The declaration ensures that “nothing shall be done which may prejudice the civil and religious rights of existing non-Jewish communities in Palestine”. British mandate after the dissolution of the Ottoman empire facilitated the establishment of a self-governing institution enabling the expropriation and expatriation of Palestinian and catalyst Nakba [Zena Tahhan]. Articles 3 and 4 of the United Nations charters envisaged a right of self-determination for the people. The British colonialization of Palestine left a devastating effect on the native. The neo-colonization forced the disposition of the Palestinians through the settlement of Jewish to convert the majority into a minority which led to the derive of decolonization and constant demand for the right of return of Arabs people to their homeland [Chapter II Article 3,4]. Though Israel was admitted as the status ‘state’ on 11 May 1948 by United Nations, Palestine’s status is yet to be determined. Resolution 43/177 dated 15 December 1988 of the UN General Assembly recognized the Palestinian Declaration of Independence and granted designation as Palestine in the UN system. More than 135 UN member countries and two non-member states have accepted Palestine as a sovereign state by July 31, 2019. Resolution 67/19 dated 29 November 2012, promoted the designation status as a non-member observer state. UNGA further decided on 17 December 2012 for use of the designation of Palestine by the Secretariats in UN documents.

The nation-state policy of Israel [Raoul Woot life]and the riots on part of the Palestinians are impediments to the amicable solution of a prolonged dispute. Though the peace process has been initiated many times stakeholders and powerful countries are continuously mediating over un-resolving prolonged conflict [Zack Beauchamp, May 2018]. The peace talks initiatives could not be succeeded unless the resolution of core issues “West Bank borders/ settlements, Israel security, Palestinian refugees, and Jerusalem ‘religiously sacred place’.

This paper is designed to collect and synthesize relevant data by using the qualitative method to explore the historical background of Palestine, and the contemporary legal status of Palestine. The cause and effect of disputes and peace mediation process.

Keywords: British mandate of Palestine, Settlement of Jewish, Palestine legal status, international peace initiatives.

INTRODUCTION

THE name ‘Palestine’ is derived from the word ‘Philistia’ and refers to the Philistines who occupied the land in the 12th century B.C. Palestine is a land of Holy Places for Muslims, Christians, and Jewish and is the most controversial region of the world.

After the dissolution of the League of Nations, Resolution 181 was adopted in the United Nations for the making of Jewish

and Arab states against the choice and acceptance of Palestinian people even though challenged by the Palestinian Lawyer before a court of law. Arabs countries disparaged and rejected the UN action while Israel accepted the resolution. The United Nations charter’s Article 10 of Chapter (iv) reflects the status of the Resolution as recommendatory not binding. Hence, Security Council resolutions 242 and 338 have made Resolution 181 unbridled.

The war started in 1948 between Israel and five Arab countries outset one day after the partition. Israel occupied 60% of the area of the Arab state proposed by the 1947 Partition Plan [Cragg, Kenneth]. Israel similarly captured the Jerusalem during Six-Day War in 1967. The Camp David Accords under the mediation of the United State witnesses the peace process and recognition of Israel by Egypt consequence of withdrawal from Sinai and the expansion of Palestinian self-government in the West Bank and Gaza. Israel also evacuated Lebanon except for the “Security Zone” near the border. The Madrid Conference of 1991 pledged the continuation of the peace process withdrawn in 1949 between Israel, Lebanon, Syria, and Palestinian [Debbie Lord et al].

The United Nations General Assembly vide Resolution 3210 (XXIX) recognized the Palestine Labor Organization (PLO) as a representative of the Palestinians on 14 October 1974 and endorsed participative rights in the General Assembly meeting on the question of Palestine [Julian Schindlerman]. Palestine was also officially known as a de jure sovereign state [Segal Jerome M], specifically an observer instead of a full member status on 22 November 1974. UNGA Resolution A/RES/67/19. 29-11-2012 signifies the “provisional status of the Palestinian Government” West Bank and Gaza. The Executive Committee of PLO represents Palestinians internationally to perform the government of the state of Palestine.

The declaration of Principal (DOP) 1993 known as the Oslo agreement was the cornerstone of two-side negotiation on the interim self-government arrangement to decide the territorial status occupied by Israel in the 1967 war except for Golan Heights. The International community hailed the efforts of the participant and the Nobel Prize was awarded to the Yasser Arafat PLO chairman, Prime Minister Yitzhak Rabin, and Israeli Foreign Minister Shimon Peres [Sarah Honig et al]. The peace process was shaken by the assignation of PM Rabin by the Israelis [Serge Schneemann]. The Camp David Accord 1978 was the base of DOP whereby self-determination of the

West Bank and Gaza strip was proclaimed, the Military government withdrew upon residential territories, the self-governing authority's election, deployment of the Palestinian police force, and the five-year transitional plan was set for resolving the status of territories [A Framework at Camp David' (1978)].

The Israeli PM, Robin, and PLO Chairman Yasser Arafat agreed "West Bank Accord" in May 1994 which cherished establishing self-rule in Gaza and Jericho and holding of Palestinian election [Ann Devroy]. The Palestinian government was established in Gaza and forty percent in the West Bank because of the Oslo agreement in 1995. The peace process was stunned due to mistrust and the uprising of the second intifada in 2000.

Palestine has certainly realized three standards and tests specified under Article 1 of the Montevideo Convention on rights and duties of the state that is defined territory, a permanent population, and a government having the capacity to build a diplomatic relationship with another state. However, Palestinian do not control the entire territory in their complete capacity due to Israel's continuous belligerency over the area designed under the portion plan of two-state and vigorous growth of settlement and pursuance for the creation of heaven land of Jewish.

Most of the international community has recognized Palestine as a state and cost voted in favor of the UN Resolution being an observer state but deprived of being a permanent member reasoning lacking one vote in the UNSC. Palestine signed several treaties and UNESCO has also admitted it as a member. Hence, Palestine is a state within a perspective of Customary International Law.

The United Nation and International Community made a stringent endeavor for a tenacious resolution of a skirmish between the two nations but over seven decades passed, the elementary causes of the dispute are aggravating day by day due to political division in the international community, Arabs support to Palestinian, and Western specifically the USA to the Israelis so, the question of Palestine recognition as a state is still unsettled.

On the intervention of US President Bush, Israel removes the settlement from Gaza but talk again discontinued over the incongruity of settlement and the issue of Palestinian prisoners during the Obama government. The worldwide political unrest arose when Donald Trump recognized Jerusalem as Israel's capital on December 6, 2017, and decided to shift the embassy there. He enlightens his plan of 'centurion peace' and tried to play a mediatory role between Arabs Countries and Israel to normalize the tension.

THESIS STATEMENT

The objective of this paper is to explore the historical background of Palestine, and the contemporary legal status of Palestine. The crucial issue to finding whether Palestine was a state in 1988. The cause and effect of disputes and peace process mediation initiatives taken by the international community and institutions to resolve the protracted conflict.

PRIMARY SOURCE

This paper is designed to collect data from SOAS's library, MLA recitation machine, academic, JSTOR, books, and Journals about the topic.

METHODOLOGY

This paper will emphasize the qualitative technique of data collection from primary sources to synthesize the embedded work to analyze and review the existing literature to fill the gaps in the descriptive method for making this paper virtuous for the stakeholder and the new researchers.

Historical Background of Palestine:

Palestine was the geographic region of the eastern Mediterranean region existing between the Mediterranean Sea and Jordon Sea comprising part of recent Israel and Palestinian territories of the Gaza Strip and West Bank till 1948. The Assyrian, Babylonian, Roman, Byzantine, and Ottoman Empires in modern history have ruled Palestine which ended with the mandate of the British [Kirk Bailey]. It is the Birthplace of Judaism and Christianity [Lipschitz, Oled]and the sacredly Holy Land for Jews, Christians, and Muslims. After World War-1, the Allied Power agreed to assign the administration of Palestine to British Mandate under the provision of Article 22 of the League of Nations covenant.

By commencing the second World War, the British governed over one-fourth of the world but later scramble down to decolonization. Though, first world war encumbrances the British economy but Second World War put the British economy in heavier debt owing to a dearth in two-thirds export resulting in obtaining a loan from the United State. The devastating economy was forced to review foreign policy. It was understood before the start of the second world war that the sun never set on the British empire [Bombshell]. British started the decolonization process and envisaged independence for colonies. The establishment of the United Nations profoundly pressurized the imperial power to peacefully leave their colonies.

Zionism is Israel's ideology, and they have a faith that Judaism is their nationality and religion. Theodor Herzl, the Australian journalist; the founder of the Zionism movement to create a Jewish homeland believed that Jewish people cannot survive without their homeland [Zack Beauchamp]. The Arabs living in Palestine for a long economically and politically suffered and confronted plenty of Jewish immigration over their native land. The first-ever census of Palestine was conducted by Ottoman Empire in 1914 and the reported population was Muslim 657000, Jewish 59000, and Christian 81000 [McCarthy Justin]. The British Mandate authorities did conduct the census on 23 October 1922 [Mills]. The stated population was 757,182 containing 590,890 Muslims, 83,794 Jews, 73,024 Christians, and the remaining other religious groups [J. B. Barron]. According to a survey carried out in 2014, there were approximately 4.3 million Palestinian living in the state of Palestine; 1.7 million

in Gaza, and 2.8 million in the West Bank. UN reported that 1.5 million Palestinian refugees live in camps in the countryside and 4 million in camps in neighboring countries. The estimated population is reported 5,178,908 by 2021[World Population Review].

Palestinians are striving to achieve their nationhood. The United Nations has considered Palestine a country and International Community as a Sovereign State. The definition of “Country” means people with citizen rights plus elected government plus land while state means only government [Stack Exchange Network]. A-State is “an independent, sovereign government exercising control over a defined territory, whose borders are usually clearly defined and internationally recognized by other states” [State, Nation, and Nation-State].

Boyle, a professor of law at Illinois university claims that “the four traditional elements comprise over territory, government, permanent population and the ability to relate in various ways and levels with other states essential to be at the centric point of Statehood” [Boyle. F]. These are the elemental qualifications test that was provided in Article-1 of the Montevideo Convention (MC) on Rights and duties of the State of 1933[Montevideo Convention on the Rights and Duties of States]. Notably, Palestine has satisfied these provisions and therefore qualifies to be a state. Most writers still observe the view that the act of recognition is not a matter governed by law, but a question of policy. They believe that recognition is the result of a decision taken not to respect as a legal duty but in fulfillment of the demands of national interest [H Lauterbach]. The State of Palestine holds prerogative over West Bank and the Gaza Strip as its territory to be a de jure (permanent and legal recognition) sovereign state with Jerusalem as its capital [Al Zoughbi, Basheer]. It is a non-member observer status in the United Nations since November 2012. This is tantamount to de facto (temporary and factual) recognition of statehood [UN Recognition of Sovereign State].

Constructive and declarative are two theories of recognition of the state. Hegel and Oppenheim have made up the Constructive theory which specifies the “State” as an international person that essentially is recognized as a state for gaining its status of an international person under international law. The declarative theory is created by Hall Wagner and Fisher and is constructed under the provision of Article 3 of the Montevideo Conference of 1933 and laid down a test for attaining recognition of statehood by another state [Mariya Paliwal].

The notion of two-nation evolved with the decolonization of Palestine on eve of the British Mandate and the canon of State Succession emerged through the transition of territory from the predecessor State to two newly created States in light of Article 2(1)(b) of Vienna Convention on the Succession State’ Grotius claimed that under Universal theory “the predecessor State passes on to new State i.e., the successor state upon succession without exception and modification”[Subodh Asthana]. Hersch also described the ethos of succession states to the mandates as prescribed by

the Treaty of Lausanne and because the treaties concluded after a war which succinctly signifies that Palestine was a newly created state [Hersch, L.]. Moreover, the Permanent Court of International Justice has also recognized the state of Palestine during its judgment regarding concessions provided by Ottoman authorities [Manley O. Hudson].

Legal Issues to the Status of Palestine as a State

The legal questions about the status of Palestine have raised several apprehensions in the past at various levels. Most of the states have accepted Palestine as an independent state. Hersch quotes the principle of succession of states to ‘A’ Mandates as laid down in the “Treaty of Lausanne”. The United Nations Partition Plan 1947 Resolution 181(II) has a contributive role regarding the separation of Palestine into two independent states: one for Jewish and another for native Arabs. Israel proclaimed independence on May 14, 1948, and officially declared as a state on the expiry of the British mandate over Palestine.

The Soviet Union recognized Israel as a De Jure country on May 17th, 1948. [Hashim S H Behbehani (1966)] The United States accepted Israel as a de facto authority on January 31st, 1949. Israel has secured permanent membership because of Security Council Resolution S/RES/69 (1949) passed on March 04, 1949 [‘S/RES/69 (1949)-S/1277’ (UN 1949)] but the issue of Palestine biassedly remained unsettled albeit, treaties of post-war widely acknowledged Palestine as a newly created state.

Israel waged war in 1948 and occupied seventy-seven percent territory of Palestine consequently, half of the Palestinians exodus from their homeland [McDowall et al]. Israel occupied the remaining territory of Palestine as the result of the 1967 war that was presently known as the West Bank and Gaza strip, which was apparently under the control of Egypt and Jordan. The Security Council’s Resolution 242 of 1969 resolved to direct Israel to vacate the Gaza Strips and West Bank.

The United Nations General Assembly in 1977 acknowledged the immutable right of Palestinians [UN Resolution 32/40B]. The Permanent Court of International Justice accepts Palestine as a sovereign state in the judgment given over concessions provided by Ottoman Authorities. Hersch supported “the legal decision adopted by the International Court of Justice” and added that “the treaty of the League of Nations has also temporarily accepted Palestinians as a nation”. It is also explained that according to the ‘theory of the succession of states, “a successor state is considered to be a sovereign state over the territorial dominion and population under the control of the previously established state and own all rights and obligations to the properties of such a rump state” [Crawford, James (2006)].

Was Palestine State in 1988?

UN Initiatives: To understand whether Palestine was a state in 1988 or not, it is expedient to put cursory insight into the development made in United Nations. UNGA resolution 181 resolved the separation of the British and commanded Palestine

into Jewish-Arabs state. Resolution 242 (1967) of the Security Council aftermath of the six-day war, demanded: “the withdrawal of the Israeli army from the occupied territory” besides respecting and acknowledging the claim of sovereignty, territorial integrity, and political freedom of every state. It was the UNSC's move to reinstate the pre-1967 borderline (territory) of the two-state.

Resolution 338 (1973) stressed upon parties to abide by unanimous UNSC Resolution 242, which means to come around to the status of pre-six days war. The UNGA Resolution 2535 (XXIV) of 10 December 1969 reaffirmed the inalienable rights of the Palestinians. Resolution 3210 (XXIV) 1974 was adopted for accepting the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO) as the representative of Palestinians in the United Nations. This manifests the salute of PLO to serve as a government for the population of Palestine.

Resolution 3236 (1974) on the question of Palestine added the Palestinian right to self-determination. Resolution 43/176 was paramount to the solemnized International Peace Conference on the middle east, titled “Question of Palestine”. The Chairman of PLO, Yasser Arafat with an accent of Palestine National Council made a unilateral declaration on December 15, 1988, for the Independence of Palestine, a state within pre-June 1967 territory, and 100 countries thereof accepted Palestine as an independent state.

Resolution 43/177 dated 15th December 1988 approved the declaration of Palestine state and occupied territories of Palestinians were called territories where Palestinian people should do exercises sovereignty.

The progress taken into United Nations proceedings manifestly reveals that Palestine fulfills the laid down criteria of statehood under customary international law, Palestine was a state as it holds a permanent population before the Christ era, having accepted the Palestinian territory of the British domain partition plan. Therefore, the Legal status of Palestine is determined through the United Nations Security Council Resolutions.

Palestine Statehood Conflict and the Peace process

The Peel Commission's suggestion in 1937 constituted to investigate the cause of unrest amongst Palestinian and Jews people and the recommendations made by the Anglo-American committee in 1946 [Anglo-American Committee of Inquiry (1946)] were controversial between the Arab League and Israelian agencies regarding the establishment of two nation-states in Palestine under the governance of the United Nations on the wake of the League of Nations. Jewish Agency for Palestine acceded to the proposal of partition plans in 1947 as well as the Peel Commission 1937 while the Arab leaders of Palestine had categorically rejected both plans, The Palestinian leadership has even not accepted the British White Paper 1939 [Malcolm MacDonald] containing promises from them to be an independent state within ten years whilst limiting Jewish settlement in Palestinian territory.

Great Britain governed Palestine in 1922, and Jewish immigration started in the region from that era. Soon after, the

end of the British Mandate over Palestine, and the Resolution for the entablement of two-state, Israel and Arabs, the Declaration of Independence on May, 14, 1948 Israel sparked conflicts between Arabs and Israel arose and caused the occurrence of the first war of 1948 between them.

The armies of four neighboring Arab countries, Jordan, Syria, Iraq, and Egypt invaded the occupied territory which area was under the control of the British Mandate [Avrahan Sela]. The war ended with the decisive victory of Israel, and Israel captured the territory of the Palestinian area including the Sinai Peninsula, Gaza Strip, West Bank, Golan Heights, and the old city of Jerusalem [Baylish Thomas].

The Armistice Agreements of 1949 constituted between Israel, Egypt, Lebanon, and Jordan for the end of violations, and hostility continued among them. They recognized the separate Greenline border under the control of the United Nations. Israel seized some areas proposed for Arab states under the partition plan [Armistice Agreements 1949]. These Greenline continued between the parties during the almost entire period of 1950 to 1967. The situation becomes worst after the attack of Israel on an Egyptian military post in Gaza in February 1965 where 37 soldiers were killed this resulted in the engagement of Palestinian volunteers fedayeen to encounter warfare against Israel, and considering this as a threat Israel launched preemptive strikes against Egypt which are known as Six-Day War fought in June 1967. Israel captured Gaza Strip from Egypt, West Bank from Jordan, and hold possession of Jerusalem, and proclaimed complete sovereignty over the captured area.

To incentivize, Palestinian existing in East Jerusalem were given citizenship of Israel. Both the parties, Israel-Palestine started negotiations under the mediation of the United State in 1991 [Carol Migdal Ovitz] but there had been no result, in the end, each round of the talk failed to leave many questions thereof, and it appeared that no such strategy can be succeeded if it lacks sincere emotion and decision of the power countries for the settlement of prolonged issue equitable suited each party. The Peel Commission Plan of the British government followed by the UN Partition Plan including Resolution 242 and the Oslo peace accords all said manifestly that the superpower was inclined toward the Jewish of Palestine rather than tended to prejudiced treatment for other parties [Nathan thrall].

The PLO Chairman, Yasser Arafat, and Israeli PM Yitzhak Rabin reached an agreement on 13th September 1993 whereby, the PLO officially accepted Israel's right of self-determination and relinquished support to terrorism. Both the parties have acknowledged the Oslo peace talks held in 1990 to find a two-state solution but there had been a huge misunderstanding between the parties regarding putting an allegation by Israeli on the matter of terrorism and valued benefit to be achieved through the Oslo peace process [Handshakes That Changed History].

Despite the assassination of Israeli PM Rabin by their right-wing Jewish on 4th November 1995 and Yahya Ayyash of Hamas, the peace process continued resulting thereby the Wye River agreement, October 1998 [Wye River Memorandum] amongst Israel and Palestine Authority for implementing the

Interim Agreement of Oslo (II) accord, 1995 [Oslo II Accord]. The Israeli parliament passed this by voting 75 in favor and 19 against it.

The Oslo plan and Camp David 2000 summit did not bear the desired result and eventually, Beirut Summit was conducted in 2002 [Beirut Summit 2002], wherein the Arab League offered an alternative political plan to truncate the Israeli-Palestine conflict and to increase harmony and relationship. The plan demanded Israel encourages an establishment of a sovereign Palestinian state and repatriation of Palestinian Refugees considering UN Resolution 194, but Israel rejected the proposal.

The Annapolis Conference, 2007 [Carol Migdal Ovitiz,] was termed a cornerstone of the two-state solution which ended with a joint statement of all concerned parties. The Obama government keeps on pressure on the Israeli government to halt the extension of Israeli settlement in the West Bank. He reiterated his commitment during his speech to the Muslim World on June 4, 2009, that "The USA would not accept the legality of Israel's settlement" in the disputed territory [BARACK OBAMA, 2009].

Netanyahu, PM of Israel stated that they would recognize the Palestinian State subject to Jerusalem remaining the united capital of Israel and accept Israel as Jewish land. Palestine shall have no armed force and Palestinian withdraw their demand for the return of refugees to their native land [Rabbi Michael Lerner]. He emphasizes the existing settlement of Jews in the West Bank is a natural process.

PM Netanyahu recalled it as a painful action that can encourage the peace process and asked the Palestinian to reflect on their positive response however, Palestinian rejected the offer. Palestinian have rapidly started a diplomatic campaign for the recognition of Palestine as an independent state within the border determined earlier in 1967 and, East Jerusalem as capital and applied for the 66th session of UNGA [Schell, Bernhard], the resolution 67/19 of November 29th, 2012, recorded categorical voting of 138 for the resolution, 9 against, and 41 abstentions.

Almost, every US President in the preceding few decades has taken an initiative to resolve the middle east crises as their top priority but has not succeeded. There are in fact some discordant issues causing disagreement in reconciliation of the agreements so far taken on the table: (a) Palestinian wants repatriation of their refugees in pursuance to the UNGA Resolution 194 (1948), the Arab initiative (2002), and according to the road map of 2003, but Israel hesitate the Palestinian refugees back to territories under its control, (b) Palestinian urge the East Jerusalem their future capital and the sovereignty of area of Haram al-Sharif (Al-Aqsa mosque), whereas Israeli claim both Eastern and Western part of Jerusalem city for undivided capital, (c) Palestinian have been treating the Israeli settlement as an illegal and wanted to be frozen in accord with an agreement of road to map, on the other end Israeli deemed the settlement necessary to their security and such as Ma' ale Adumim are the part of Israel, (d) Palestinian demand of pre-1967 border which shall not be truncated by settlement enclave, wall and fences divided Israel from Gaza,

and more than ninety percent of the West Bank. Israel demanded complete control over border, airspace, and water, albeit has not yet decided how much land be left for the Palestine state, Palestinian on other hand having a quasi-state in occupied territories with the functioning of their own Parliament, Administration, Investigation Agencies, Court of Law and the Interior and Foreign Ministries.

The Motion for recognition was placed by President Mahmoud Abbas on November 29, 2012; the UNGA approve the motion while granting the status of Palestine as a non-member observer state which is just symbolic. The Security Council ascending is pending and the decision was labeled by the Israeli Government as a unilateral act [Ashkar et al] and claiming that Palestine's state only comes into existence if Palestine concludes a peace negotiation with Israel [Dorel Oren].

Effect of Recognition of Palestine.

Palestinian are constantly endeavoring for recognition as a sovereign state with the international organizations and community. Palestine Liberation Organization since its establishment in 1964, seeking international support for recognition of Palestine as State for resolving the two-nation protracting conflict and they considered the USA's support very essential in this regard.

The United States has recognized the PLO but not the state of Palestine [JTA]. Presidential waiver happened during the creation of the Palestine National Agency in 1994 in as the result of the Oslo agreement, and the PLO office was redesignated as PLO mission, and subsequently "general Delegation of PLO Mission" in 2010 but suspended in 2018. PLO office mission was established in Washington DC in 1994 [Trump Administration Closes PLO's Office in Washington].

The relationship between the US and Palestine had never been satisfactory since the creation of PLO during the administration of Gerald Ford (1974 to 1977), James earl carter junior (1977 to 1981), Ronald Wilson Reagan (1981 to 1989), George Herbert Walker Bush (1989 to 1993), William Jefferson Clinton (1993 to 2001), George Walker Bush (2001 to 2009), Barak Hussain Obama (2009 to 2017) and Trump (2017 to 2020).

The President of the US has opened various negotiation avenues but one another ended unsuccessfully due to certain reasons, preempt conditioned to the acceptance of Israel by Palestine, halt of insurgency activity, and abandonment of the right of return claim of Palestinians. Seventy percent of the International Community out of 135 United Nations member states have already recognized the state of Palestine, the remaining states are considering doing so. Antonio Guterres stated Resolving the Israeli-Palestinian conflict is "key to sustainable peace in the Middle East" [Antonio Guterres]. Recognition of Palestine is a source for resolving the Israel-Palestine conflict which would be in the interest of the United State and the International community. Francoise Delattre, a Representative of France in the United Nation has stated that Israel/Palestine conflict is a permanent threat to International Security [speakers in Security Council].

The Swedish and British have officially decided to recognize

the state of Palestine. The European Union states feel their responsibility to support the Palestinian cause of self-determination and make constant efforts for a two-state solution for the settlement of unresolvable disputes. This was indeed a paradigm change that the European state's opinion adverted in support of a free Palestine and Sweden and the British increased moral pressure on Israel to withdraw from the occupation [Mustafa Barghouti], it was also considered that the independence of Palestinians is a domestic and international truth that Palestinians can do through the participation of all forums of the UN and treaties including the International Criminal court and desist from all forms of violation.

The Palestinians have signed the Geneva Convention which specifies the rules of warfare and humanitarian operation in the conflict zone. The Palestinians also requested to adhere to the decision of the Vienna convention held on diplomatic relations, and an anti-corruption agreement [AF and TOI staff]. The Palestinian president, Mahmoud Abbas applied for joining the fifteen international treaties and conventions [Palestinian Intent to Accede to 15 Treaties]. Ambassador Hesham Youssef's observation contended on 'the Israeli-Palestinian conflict 2020, the possible way forward; though tremendous efforts made since the 1991 Madrid Peace conference to resolve the Israeli-Palestinian conflict through a two-state solution, peace has been elusive. He examines the potential scenarios facing Israelis, Palestinians, and the region as a stalemated conflict continued without progress toward two states [Ambassador Hesham Youssef].

As a matter concerning the recognition of the Palestinian state, Mr. Mahmoud Abbas, the president of the Palestine Authority (PA) sought a full member-state status based upon the pre-1967 line. UNSC being a recommendatory forum to accord approval of the new state as a full member status in the United Nation, consumed two months and finally resolved to make a unanimous recommendation on the petition of Palestine. Spinning down to an earlier position. Abbas made a request to the UNGA for admission of an application to Palestine as a Non-member Observer Status likewise as a position that was given to the Vatican. This resolution 2334 held on December 23rd, 2016, is treated to be corn stone for world peace whereby it has been resolved that Israeli settlement activity is constituting a "flagrant violation" of International Law and this settlement ambition is not legally valid. It was urged therein that Israel should stop such activity and fulfill an obligation of occupying power under the 4th Geneva Convention.

The conflicting plight of Israeli-Palestinian is so crucial and threatening to world security and If peace is ever to be desired, it is obligatory upon the world community to demonstrate for the demand an end to violations of international law. Both sides should be given a forum to voice their concerns about the dilemma of their people, be it security, human rights, or anything else, but they must not be allowed to disrupt the law. UN Security Council should also enforce the international rule of law regarding resolving the issue. When establishing UN operations, the council should give greater weight to establishing the rule of law. America shall be impartial and not have to wield its power of veto power. It is almost forty times

to block efforts to call Israel to account for its violations of the Geneva Conventions, the Nuremberg models [Nuremberg Trials], a frequent human rights convention, and numerous directives of the Security Council, and let the UN regulate its faint presence in this dispute.

The tension once rejuvenated when on December 6, 2017, US President Donald Trump declared the recognition of Jerusalem as the capital of Israel and shifted the US Embassy from Tel Aviv to Jerusalem [Landler, Mark]. Mahmoud Abbas, the President of Palestine in a speech observed that the US was "abdicating its role as a peace mediator". Palestinians considered Jerusalem a Holy place and will never accept this US decision. The international communities widely criticized Trump's Jerusalem decision including European and US allies. China observed the danger of the potential escalation of tension in the Middle East and Pope Francis asserted that all nations remain committed to respecting the status quo of the Holy City [Horowitz, Jason].

US President Donald Trump revealed his vision of a "peace plan" for the Middle East and stated that as a "deal of the century". Palestinian leadership renounce the plan percept to its release and abstained from the presence [Trump-Unveiled Israeli-Plan]. The two-state plan contained various proposals, these acclaimed by the Israeli PM Netanyahu as "a great plan for Israel, it is a great peace plan", He added that "Trump was the greatest friend that Israel has ever had in the White House". There had been a huge reaction around the world over the plan.

On 18 December 2017, the UNSC resolution called for the withdrawal of the recognition with a vote of 14-1. US vetoes vote. The UNGA Resolution ES-10/L.22 of 21st December 2017 condemned the US declaration for change of the status of Jerusalem as the capital of Israel, and none of the NATO allies opposed the Resolution [Glad Stone, Rick]. The majority of the Organization of Islamic Corporation (OIC) in a meeting held on December 13, 2017, in Istanbul condemned trump's decision. and called for withdrawal. Mahmoud Abbas stated in his speech that the US no longer fit as a fair negotiator for Middle East peace being biased in the settlement of the two-state dispute [MC Kernan, Bethan].

The Palestinian President, Abbas sneered at the plan as a conspiracy that cannot be sustained. The Hamas official, Sami Abu Zuhr described the said proposal as worthless and goes into the dustbin. Martin Indyk an American diplomat who has served as Ambassador to Israel stated that Trump's proposal is not viable because the Palestinians will not accept it. He reiterated that the right-wing Jewish party vehemently opposed Palestine as a state and was not ready for giving even a small piece of land in the West Bank. The U.S.'s decision to recognize all settlements on the West Bank is an active violation on part of Israel under international law [U.S. Says Settlement Products Can Be Labelled "Made in Israel"].

The world's longest conflict lingering in the past seventy-three years between Israel and the Palestinians is looking unresolved even Trump's peace plan will be deemed futile, and it is quite possible, it could not yield benefit to anyone [Robin Wright].

I. CONCLUSION

It is evident from the above study that Palestine has positively realized three standards and tests specified under Article-1 of the Montevideo Convention on Rights and Duties of States; defined Territory, Permanent population, Government, and the capacity to build a diplomatic relationship with another state.

However, Palestinians do not control territory in their complete capacity due to Israeli continuous belligerency over an area designed under a partition plan of two-state and vigorous growth of settlement for the creation of a heaven-land for the Jewish. The contemporary concept of defined territory took a paradigm shift; thus, this is not an essential question. Hence, Palestine is a state with the perspective of customary International Law having attained independence under the UN partition Plan after the end of the British mandate to Palestine and entitled to all property rights being successors in interest and qualified for the pre-requisite test and standards of International Law.

Most of the international community has recognized Palestine as a state and cast a vote in favor of the UNGA resolution being an observer state but deprived of being permanent member reasoning to lacking one vote in favor of the UNSC. Palestine signed several treaties and UNESCO admitted it as a member. Hence, Palestine is a state with the perspective of customary International Law having attained independence under UN partition Plan after the end of the British mandatory to Palestine and entitled to all property rights being successor in interest and qualified the pre-requisite test and standards.

Almost every US President in the past few decades is taking initiative on their top priority to resolve the Middle conflict but not so for success. There are some discordant issues causing disagreement in the reconciliation of the agreements so far taken on the table. Trump's plan for a two-state peace process without the concurrence of Palestine invoked worldwide opinion in favor and criticism even from home.

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